

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Wobo**FIRST NAME:** Emmanuel**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Writing a Good Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 7- 13)
2. The Use of American and British English in Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 41-42)
5. Rule of Thumb (EUCLID 2021, 11-14)
6. Grammarly and Zotero Writing and Referencing Tools

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

It took great courage to decide on this doctoral pursuit with Euclid University. I had demonstrated some procrastination, primarily due to my work schedule and location, my fear of being inadequate, and other family and social demands. Eventually, when I started, I was inundated with so much information about the school and program expectations. The university's systematic explanation of the learning process and anticipated outcome motivated me more. They achieved this by giving me all the necessary tools and resources, including video tutorials that increased my understanding and broadened my perspective.

The first-course period, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenwerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, was an introduction to international academic writing for doctoral students, covering the essential elements required to prepare for their dissertations and effectively write publishable academic papers.

Other elements discussed include using American and British English in academic writing, plagiarism, style guide, the rule of thumb, and using Grammarly and Zotero essay writing and referencing tools.

As a follow-up to EUCLID's requirements, this response paper for period one will focus on better understanding the use of materials and resources provided and their application.

The university's resources provided a better understanding of students' odious expectation(s) of a doctoral student; a systematic methodology and or approach is elaborated, along with other strident processes and procedures expected of a doctoral student was included. Reading and writing tools like the Grammarly app for MS Word, Zotero, WHO writing and referencing style, Turabian referencing style, processes on how to complete a qualitative dissertation, various methodologies on how to conduct and write a good research and dissertation with an emphasis on chapter three, rubrics on how to evaluate the quality of a qualitative dissertation and literature review, among others.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

The course period one, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenwerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, was an introduction to international academic writing for doctoral students. They outlined the essential elements for good essay writing to prepare students for their dissertations and effectively write publishable academic work.

Essay writing is when an author or writer gives a logical argument or narrative. There are different types of essay writing, but for this course, the focus will be on academic writing, which (EUCLID 2021, 7) described as "nonfictional writing produced as an academic work." They identified some forms of academic writing, including research findings, books, newspapers, and periodicals.

They further asserted that academic essay writing focuses on problems or hypotheses to obtain an objective conclusion not just by making assumptions but rather by using critical thinking and well-informed research where the intended finding is consistent with the advised style, accurate, and exact.

To create a solid academic article that effectively communicates ideas and responds to my hypothesis, I want to use this as a guide and the structure of my dissertation strategy as I progress in the program.

3) THE USE OF AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH IN ACADEMIC WRITING

English is widely used for trade and commerce in most parts of the world. It is also the official language of the United States (US) and the United Kingdom (UK).

There are, however, some levels of differences and similarities, as well as preferences in terms of usage and acceptability. Accordingly, EUCLID (2021, 25) noted that since World War II, American English has progressively increased in importance

abroad, growing along with American political, economic, technological, and cultural impact around the world. Due in significant part to the following, American English today has the most influence on "global English" (compared to British English). Globally, they both have American and British variants, and they are more "alike" than distinct, especially when using "learned" or "scientific" English. However, their natural history and cultural development is attributed to most of the variations.

Noticeable differences can be found in "Difference in Pronunciation but same Spelling" and "Difference in "Spelling but same Pronunciation."

4) PLAGIARISM

Unauthorized usage of another person's work harms the ability to produce high-caliber academic writing. Additionally, it calls into doubt the author's and the scholarly paper's honesty. As a result, it is defined as using the information without referencing or acknowledging the work's original creator (EUCLID 2021, 25). In support of this, Bloomberg and Volpe (2019, 92) added that adequate referencing and citation "provides readers with a rapid resource for discovering and accurately accessing all sources that were used" during the writing of the piece.

Plagiarism comes in different forms- like using someone else's words or ideas without giving them due credit; this occurs when you quote without appropriately referencing it when you paraphrase, copy, and paste from the internet. Plagiarism would also happen when you have a paper written for you or hand in an article you did not author, put your name on it, and give it to your professor (EUCLID 2021, 34)

To avoid plagiarism, you credit an author using an "In-Text Citation and List of Work Cited" or Bibliography and Reference List when you quote or paraphrase their work; also included is the use of graphs and data from the internet that is not originally yours.

Accordingly, Turabian (2007, 18.3.1) averred that information from a source must be cited and referenced using the parenthetical citation format.

It has been established that plagiarism is both unethical and a serious academic offense, and I intend to avoid falling into this trap as I progress in the program. As noted earlier, I will ensure that my essay and other academic works are properly cited, and all authors and sources used while developing my work will be acknowledged.

5) STYLE GUIDE

There are procedures for writing in various disciplines, and for this course, E provided us with their standard academic writing style guide, which has to do with their approved style of writing and formatting.

A style guide is a reference book that provides rules for writing, such as grammar and syntax, in specific disciplines. They include how to format citations and references, which are particular to the fields of study. EUCLID (2021, 5) also noted that a "style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output."

They added that academic writing covers many aspects of a report, like, font usage, heading style, structure, voice preferences, trademark, and brand considerations.

The Turabian or Chicago and other recommended writing styles will be further studied, ingrained, and used as my preferred style for consistency in my writing approach.

6) GRAMMARLY AND ZOTERO WRITING AND REFERENCING TOOL

One of the reasons why I started this doctoral program was to improve on my previous achievements, increase my self-esteem, advance my carrier, and significantly improve my communication and writing skills to a level expected of a doctoral student.

Being introduced and exposed to these writing and referencing tools has renewed my confidence and belief that I can achieve my aim in this program if I focus and put in more effort.

With the proper application of the in-built features in Grammarly, I will give my writing the required voice, clarity, and originality. Also included in the features are a plagiarism detector, word choice, writing style suggestions, punctuation, and spell checking.

Zotero also came in handy, like the insight gained from the Grammarly video tutorial. Zotero also gave me a better perspective on referencing, such as the in-text Citation and bibliography capabilities.

Zotero also has some added features, including a web browser Plug-in, Downloading PDF Text from the internet, support for various citation styles, and a Micro Soft Word Plug-in.

7) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one, as revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, was very insightful. Their style of introducing students to the various topics for the period and their requirements was evident. The tutorial video by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck demonstrated how to use Styles, formatting, and their application in MS Word documents. Dr. Kabiru Gulma also demonstrated how to track changes and review papers in Microsoft Word.

Euclid University provided the necessary tools and resources to prepare for my doctoral pursuit. The first-course period, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenwerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, introduces international academic writing for postgraduate students.

The response paper for period 1 focused on a better understanding the use of materials and resources provided and their application. The university's resources provided a systematic methodology, approach, and other strident processes and procedures expected of a doctoral student.

American English was the preferred style to use in this period.

American English has increased in importance abroad due to its influence on "global English" and its natural history and cultural development.

Plagiarism is the unauthorized use of someone else's work without permission, raising questions about the integrity of the academic paper and its author. It is defined as using information without referencing or acknowledging the work's original creator. It is vital to credit an author using an "In-Text Citation and List of Work Cited" or Bibliography and Reference List to ensure that all authors and sources used while developing the work are cited.

Euclid provided a style guide for academic writing and gave rules for grammar and syntax, as well as how to format citations and references. Academic writing covers many aspects, including font usage, heading style, structure, voice preferences, trademark, and brand considerations. The Turabian or Chicago style will be used as a preferred writing style for consistency

The introduction of Grammarly and Zotero to the doctoral program has given me renewed confidence and increased self-esteem. These tools gave my writing, voice, clarity, and originality, as well as plagiarism detector, word choice, writing style suggestions, punctuation, and spell checking. Zotero has added features, such as a web browser Plug-in, Downloading PDF Text from the internet, and Micro Soft Word Plug-in.

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